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Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional **MED**iterranean **Grape**, **OL**ive and **Durum** wheat food systems

Deliverable 3.6

First feedback report from users on wine pilot service development

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report accounts for Deliverable 3.6, “First feedback report from users on wine pilot service development”. This document contains the outcomes of the first feedback workshop, directly focused on the interaction between the end-users and the beta version of the wine pilot service tool. The workshop was held at SOGRAPE headquarters in Avintes, Vila Nova de Gaia, and involved 12 decision makers from the company. The objectives of the workshop were to present the current version of the tool to the users, collect their views on its features as well as clarifying some concepts in order to improve the tool during the forthcoming refinement phase.

On one side, the scientific teams from ENEA, BSC and NOA wanted to gather feedback from SOGRAPE’s staff on the applicability and relative importance of the predictions of essential climate variables, bioclimatic indicators and risk indices. Furthermore, multiple visualizations of the tool were presented so the users could choose the most useful version. Information about potential changes that could improve the usability of the tool was also gathered. More specifically, there were particular discussions on the best color scales, the value of using terciles against percentiles for the representation of predicted probabilities and the convenience of single point predictions vs. maps.

The workshop was conducted by MED-GOLD members at the University of Leeds and SOGRAPE, who also compiled the conclusions. BSC, NOA and ENEA constructed the proposed examples and the list of questions to answer from the end-users. The value of the information provided depended on the department but, in general, all visualizations were deemed useful at some point. Moreover, the users highlighted that the blue-red was preferable for temperature-based bioclimatic indicators and essential climate variables, green-brown for precipitation and the ‘traffic light’ scale (red-yellow-green) for the risk indices.

These outcomes will be taken into account in the next phase of the tool’s development. The scientific teams can improve the provision of the information both at seasonal and climate projection time scales. These improvements will be tested again during the second round of end-user feedback that it is planned in nine months time (April 2020, month 28 of the project).

With this deliverable, the project has contributed to the achievement of the following objectives (DOA, PartB Table1.1):

No.	Objective	Yes
1	To co-design, co-develop, test, and assess the added value of proof-of-concept climate services for olive, grape, and durum wheat	X
2	To refine, validate, and upscale the three pilot services with the wider European and global user communities for olive, grape, and durum wheat	
3	To ensure replicability of MED-GOLD climate services in other crops/climates (e.g., coffee) and to establish links to policy making globally	
4	To implement a comprehensive communication and commercialization plan for MED-GOLD climate services to enhance market uptake	X
5	To build better informed and connected end-user communities for the global olive oil, wine, and pasta food systems and related policy making	X

1. INTRODUCTION

Seasonal predictions and long-term climate information are critical for several aspects of decision-making in the wine sector, such as pest management and vineyard plantation planning. MED-GOLD seeks to create innovative climate services to adapt the agricultural management to the supporting information provided on these time scales. The service proposed for the wine sector comes in the form of an online platform tool that centralizes and coordinates the information accessible to the end-users.

In this framework, SOGRAPE provides the scientific partners (ENEA, BSC, NOA and Met Office) with guidance for the seasonal- and long-term configuration of the tool, both at case-study level as well as on the visualization characteristics and selection of the most relevant climatic, bioclimatic and extreme climate indices. In this framework, this report collects the outcomes of the first round of SOGRAPE end-user feedback on the beta version of the tool. More specifically, the scientific partners provided different ways of displaying the information (concept samples) that were discussed with the end-users.

These concept samples were based on the information gathered during the first round of focus groups (see deliverable 3.1), that is to say, on figures and maps depicting seasonal climate predictions and climate projections of essential climate variables (maximum and minimum temperature, mean temperature, precipitation), bioclimatic indicators (GST, GDD, SprR, SU35, WSDI;), and a risk index that merges the information of different bioclimatic indicators to gauge how good / bad a particular year has been / could be. These products have been developed using climatic data from the Santa Barbara weather station, ECMWF System 5 seasonal predictions and climate projections from EURO-CORDEX. The selection of good and bad years was proposed as a result of the work done following the first focus group (selected bad years were 1988, 1993 and 2002 whereas selected good years were 2007 and 2011).

1.1. PURPOSE

The objective of this deliverable is to summarise the results of the first feedback workshop where SOGRAPE end-users were presented with different approaches to seasonal and long-term predictions from the beta version of the tool for the wine sector. This workshop allowed the scientific partners to have insights on the level of understanding of information by end-users and at the same time, to identify the best way to convey information for decision-making (e.g. type of visualisations preferred by end-users). This information is critical for the subsequent phase of the project where the tool will be further improved in accordance to end-user needs and expectations.

1.2. SCOPE

Agriculture is very sensitive to climate variability, extremes and impacts of climate change. Seasonal and long-term climate predictions are one of the tools available to allow end-users to adapt their decision making strategies, e.g. using temperature and precipitation information from one to several months into the future. MED-GOLD seeks to adapt the agricultural management of three staple crops of the Mediterranean diet: durum wheat, grapes and olives to the supporting information provided at these time scales. The co-development of the climate services' tool for the wine sector involves collaboration between scientific partners and decision-makers through specially designed interaction workshops.

1.3. DEFINITIONS AND ACRONYMS

1.3.1. DEFINITIONS

Concepts and terms used in this document and needing a definition are included in Table 1-1. These definitions were also used and shown to users at the beginning of the workshop, so that they could fully understand the ensuing discussion.

Table 1-1 Definitions

Concept / Term	Definition
Climate models	Models that simulate the interactions of the important drivers of climate (e.g. atmosphere, oceans, land surface, ice)
Seasonal forecasts	Forecasts ranging from months to years in the future
Climate change projections	Projections of climate decades in the future
Essential Climate Variables	Basic variables used to characterise the earth's climate
Indicator	A parameter describing a reality, i.e., synthesizing the effects of future climate change with relevance to a specific sector and business
Index	An aggregation of different indicators
Tercile	Division of a distribution of a sample into three categories
Percentile	Division of a distribution of a population in 100 categories

1.3.2. ACRONYMS

Acronyms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Table 1-2 Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
ECV	Essential Climate Variables
EU	European Union
COP21	21 st Conference of the Parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (held in Paris in 2015)
DDR	Douro Demarcated Region
DWR	Douro Wine Region
MED-GOLD	Project “Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional MEDiterranean Grape, Olive and Durum wheat food systems”
WP	Work Package
GST	Growing Season Temperature
GDD	Growing Degree Days
SprR	Spring Rain
SU35	Number of heat stress days
WSDI	Warm Spell Duration Index

2. REFERENCES

2.1 REFERENCE DOCUMENTS

The following documents, although not part of this document, amplify or clarify its contents. Reference documents are referenced in this document in the form [RD.x]:

Table 2-1 Reference Documents

Ref.	Title	Date
[RD.1]	Deliverable 1.6 - Guidelines for appraising needs and critical decisions across the pilot services	2018
[RD.2]	Deliverable 1.7 - Guidelines for collecting feedback from the users involved in the development of the pilot services	2019
[RD.3]	Deliverable 3.1 - Report on the two case studies at seasonal- and long-term timescales for the wine sector	2018

3. PARTICIPATORY WORKSHOP

A workshop format was selected to gather feedback from the end-users of the company on the beta version of the tool. The workshop was prepared following the guidelines put forward in D1.7. It took place on the 27th of May 2019 at SOGRAPE's facilities in Avintes, Vila Nova de Gaia, and lasted for 2.5 hours. Considering the time available, the preparation of the workshop involved several telcos and collaborative work among the scientific partners (ENEA, BSC and NOA), SOGRAPE and the University of Leeds, to condense and present the information in such a way that all the points could be covered successfully. The workshop was organized around a U-shaped table with the moderators sitting across the open end. All participants having signed authorizations, the whole session was recorded on video for later reference. In the following lines we summarise the workshop, focusing on the main topics and outcomes discussed.

3.1. INTRODUCTION

The workshop involved the participation of 12 staff members from SOGRAPE, who came from different areas within the company and held various positions. Most of them were not familiar with the MED-GOLD project and hadn't taken part in the Focus Group meeting held in May 2018. Consequently, there were some doubts on their level of understanding of some key concepts such as 'tercile', 'percentile' or 'climate model' as well as the scope and objectives of the project.

Hence, the first part of the workshop was devoted to introduce the aim and purpose of MED-GOLD (by Marta Soares, University of Leeds), and the specific objectives of WP3, which is the package devoted to the development of the wine climate service. Afterwards, the following concepts were introduced:

- Climate models
- Seasonal forecasts
- Essential climate variables
- Indicator
- Index
- Tercile
- Percentile

It was somewhat surprising how keen the staff members were on understanding the concepts presented. This is due to the training strategy carried out by SOGRAPE's MED-GOLD Team (led by Antonio Graça), who has been performing a thorough facilitation task within the company.

3.2. DISCUSSION ON THE VISUALIZATION OF THE PILOT SERVICES

In this section, four different types of pilot output products were shown to participants and their feedback was recorded. The pilot products were focused on the case study of 2002 (identified as a bad year) for the Douro Demarcated Region (DDR). This year was selected in an aleatory form.

Example 1:

Probability of terciles for AMJ precipitation 2002. Start date 1st April. Calibrated ECMWF SEAS5

Figure 3-1: Seasonal forecast for daily mean precipitation in April-May-June (AMJ) 2002 in the Douro region (April start date; lead 0). The graphic contains the probabilities of the terciles and the observed value.

Example 2:

Most likely tercile for AMJ precipitation 2002. Start date 1st April. Calibrated ECMWF SEAS5

Figure 3-2: **Left:** Seasonal forecast for precipitation in April-May-June 2002 in Europe (April start date; lead 0) using terciles. Coloured areas show the most likely precipitation category and its percentage probability to occur. These categories show where the model improve upon the current approach using the climatology (areas with skill). Areas without skill are unshaded. **Right:** observed risk index for the Douro region in 2002, calculated using data from E-OBS.

Example 3:

Figure 3-3: Map and colourbar depicting the seasonal prediction of the Spring Rain index in the Douro region for 2002 (April start date; lead 0) using percentiles (colourbar) and terciles (map).

The preference of the workshop participants was to get the products as maps (example 3). They quickly excluded examples 1 and 2. In example number 4 they found difficult to imagine how the information in the percentile colorbars could be useful for them. Some even regarded the percentile depictions as a bit 'confusing'. However, they finally agreed that, whenever possible, the most useful visualisation would be the one with the percentiles along with a map and explanatory text. They also provided some feedback on the colours, giving some examples of what colours would work best in different representations:

- Temperature: blue and red gradient.
- Precipitation: green and brown gradient.
- Risk index: green/yellow/red traffic light system.

3.3. PILOT SERVICE BASED ON SEASONAL PREDICTIONS

In the next part of the workshop, the three layers of information available were introduced: risk indices, bioclimatic indicators and essential climate variables, with the aim to explain the connection among these products (see Figure 3-4).

Figure 3-4: Scheme of the three layers of available information: risk indices, bioclimatic indicators and essential climate variables.

For seasonal products, different information was shown to participants (only bioclimatic and risk layers). Initially, the bioclimatic indicators for the selected years were presented as percentile bars, with the purpose of verifying the value of the simulations and validating them against participants' memories (Figure 3-5). Actually, the objective was not only to catch the attention of the end-users, but also to start building trust by showing them that the indicators match their own memories of the situations in those years.

Figure 3-5: Example of different colorbars introduced to the end-users depicting different bioclimatic indicators along with the good and bad years. AMJJASO means the period April to October.

With the aim to show how the maps looked like for bioclimatic indicators, an example was shown for all the case study years (Figure 3-6).

Figure 3-6: Observed Spring Rain percentile categorization for the case study years in the Douro region. E-OBS dataset.

Risk indices (sanitary and heat indices), built through the aggregation of bioclimatic indicators, were also presented to end-users (sanitary index in Figure 3-7, 3-8).

Figure 3-7: Predicted most likely tercile for the Sanitary Risk Index seasonal forecast for 2002 (25 ensemble members). Start date: April. Lead time: 0. for Douro region.

Figure 3-8: Observed Sanitary Risk Index in the Douro region for 2002, as calculated from the E-OBS dataset.

The potential of seasonal forecasts for decision-making was highlighted by the high interest shown by the end-users. The evaluation went through the three layers of information available:

- **ECVs:** in addition to temperature and precipitation, the users would like to have information on wind, radiation and relative humidity. They would be satisfied to receive this information as terciles with a prediction 6 months into the future (next season), even though percentiles would be their preferred choice.
- **Bioclimatic indicators:** the users would like to have an indicator for precipitation during the winter months (WintR), and even another one for the number of cold/frost days. However, they are aware that the forecast of cold/frost days is difficult. They would like to receive this information for the next 6 months or the next 3 months if the probabilities of each tercile are high enough (i.e. above 70%).
- **Risk indices:** these indices were perceived as useful for the more technical aspects of production (e.g. oenology or viticulture). The users would like to receive the first forecast for both indices (Sanitary Risk Index and Heat Index) 6 months before harvest time (with the viticulture department interested in receiving it in February for the next 6 months).

3.4. PILOT SERVICE BASED ON CLIMATE PROJECTIONS

When dealing with climate projection pilot visualization the end-users found the reading of the maps very intuitive. They found projections with relative values (in comparison to present climate) more useful than maps showing absolute values.

The users would also like to add a layer of information on altimetry to help them better estimate the potential implications of the future changes of ECVs. Another suggestion was the inclusion of total annual precipitation as another ECV.

This type of service was perceived as useful, for example, in the selection of grape variety, market opportunities and adaptation strategies in the company (e.g. human resources). On the other hand, end-users think that projecting the risk indices has no useful application.

Figure 3-9: Projected Spring Rain scenarios for the Douro region for the periods 2031-2060 and 2071-2100, as percentage differences from the baseline climate (1971-2000). The absolute values for the baseline climate are shown in the upper left panel. Source: CORDEX.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable reports the feedback obtained during a workshop held to gather the opinions from 12 decision makers in SOGRAPE regarding different aspects of the beta version of the wine climate service tool.

After introducing some relevant technical concepts, the users were presented with different visualization options of climate-related information, dealing with maps, graphs and colour bars. Their preferred choice was the use of maps along with tercile/percentile plots and explanatory text. They also selected the blue-red gradient as preferred colour scheme for temperature. On the other hand, for the risk indices, the 'traffic light' approach (red-yellow-green) was favoured.

A progressive disclosure of information was suggested (consisting in providing the option to access information gradually rather than all at once). This leaves to the user to decide to go only for the risk index or proceed further to see the information on the bioclimatic indicators and/or the essential climate variables. This is an important aspect that allows accommodating different user needs. For instance, departments with lower technical profiles (e.g., hosting, human resources) highlighted that a simple text description would be adequate for them, and that they could be overwhelmed if 'forced' to select what they need from all the available information.

Regarding seasonal forecasts, the users understood that using terciles provides a more reasonable representation of the prediction (due to the limited amount of ensemble members currently available), and accepted it as the minimum, but indicated that the ideal situation would be percentiles. They highly valued the possibility to have essential climate variables up to six months ahead, and noted that, if possible, they would appreciate having forecasts for wind, radiation and relative humidity.

It is worth noting that the usefulness of these seasonal forecasts is more relevant to the technical users of the production side of the company. There was no potential to use them in marketing and commercial areas, as they plan for a minimum of 9 months ahead.

Interestingly, the technical users set a minimum of 70% probability for a tercile to trigger a particular decision, assuming that the prediction has some skill. Finally, they expect the forecasts to be issued in February / March spanning across the next 6 months and being updated every month (or 3-months, if this approach improves the skill).

Bioclimatic indicators have more relevance to the operational activities of the company. There is less understanding on how these indicators could be useful at seasonal time-scales for the non-technical departments. In this regard, users would appreciate the calculation of additional indicators, and mentioned total winter precipitation, cold spells and frost days (they are aware that this might be difficult).

Turning to climate projections, the end-users are interested in the relative increase / decrease of the variables, both ECVs and bioclimatic indicators. However, they are not interested in projections of the risk indices. They would also like to have a layer of altimetry superimposed on the maps because they work at the local level. As an example of the utility of projections, they explained they can be useful when choosing grape varieties or deciding on adaptation strategies within the company.

The outcomes of the first feedback workshop are part of task 3.3 'Testing the tool' and set the fundamentals for the first improvement phase of the pilot service that is part of task 3.2 'Developing the tool'. These improvements will be tested again during the second round of end-user feedback that it is planned in nine months time (April 2020, month 28 of the project).

ANNEX A. AGENDA

27/05/2019

10:30 - 10:40	The Med-Gold project and the wine pilot services
10:40 - 11:10	Options for visualising the pilot services 1
11:10 - 12:00	Pilot service 1 based on seasonal climate forecasts
12:00 - 12:30	Pilot service 2 based on climate change projections
12:30 - 12:45	Wider discussion
12:45 - 13:00	Recap and next steps

ANNEX B. PARTICIPANTS

Participant	Position	Main responsibilities
Antonio Braga	Director of Oenology	- Maturation control planning - Setting harvest dates
Flora Couso	Director of Human Resources	-Responsible for human resources recruitment management, personnel administrative management, training and documentation.
Joana Bahia	Project Management	-Manage corporate transversal projects, accompanying teamwork.
Joana Sarmento	Brand Activation & Consumer Events	-Planning, organization and execution of outdoor events
João Porto	Director of Viticulture	- Choice of grapevine's rootstock and clone for planting - Definition of training and pruning system -Cropping operations' planning and management - Management of agricultural machinery according to operational planning
Luis C. Almeida	Director of Oenology	-Maturation control planning - Setting harvest dates
Luis Simões	Director of Quality and Safety	-Responsible for Quality, Environment and Food Safety requirements and comply with all legal and regulatory requirements. Coordinator of Sogrape's sustainability program.
Marta Azevedo	Communication & Public Relations	-Responsible for the execution of strategic communication process between the organization and clients and consumers.
Miguel Pessanha	Administrator	- Choice of region and site for establishment of new vineyards - Choices of grapes varieties for planting
Paulo Prior	Director of Oenology	- Maturation control planning - Setting harvest dates
Pedro Pinto	Director of Property Maintenance and General Service	- Responsible for the management, maintenance and construction of new structures of the company's assets
Rute Sousa	Innovation manager	- Project management and innovation initiatives.

END OF DOCUMENT

